

Development of Data Encryption Algorithm in Information Computer Security Systems for Optimal Performance

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Abstract : This paper presents the development of data encryption algorithm (DEA) in information computer security systems. The rapid development of information in computer technology has brought about the wide spread use of the internet. However, issues relating to information security becomes paramount in the areas of information storage and data transmission. Data encryption standards is an effective and efficient component that ensures the secure communication between different entities by transferring information that only the authorized recipient can access it. The technique adopted involves the use of triple data encryption algorithm using MATLAB/SIMULINK. The results obtained shows that an average response times of 874.08sec, 157.84sec and 147.30sec produced the throughput values of 33.91Mb/sec, 187.80Mb/sec and 201.24Mb/sec, respectively. These results revealed that triple data encryption algorithm (TDEA) with double exclusive OR (DXOR) provides an enhanced encryption schemes in terms of security strength and execution time when compared with DEA. However, TDEA with DXOR algorithm had excellent avalanche effect and performed better than DEA and TDEA without DXOR.

Keywords: Data encryption algorithm, Computer security, triple data encryption algorithm, throughput, MATLAB/SIMULINK

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1.0 Introduction

The application of internet technology has revolutionized our environment with great changes in the life of the people, job activity and organizations. Data security is the most essential issues of lawful and actual entities. Nowadays, unauthorized users to sensitive data is the most significant challenges that affect data distribution in internet. Sensitive information such as credit card information, customers account details and private information in an organization should be

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protected from unauthorized persons (Sivan, 2021).

However, most of the communication is performed using electronic media and there is increase in data handling in computer network. Again, communication technology capable of holding great mass of data and information need to be exchanged by public communication networks. Recently, many users generate and interchange large volumes of information in various fields through the internet. The use of cryptography techniques are useful in wireless security such as mobile telephony and military communications that require greater prominence on the speed of communication (Devanshu, 2018).

Cryptography make use of secret codes which enable the confidentiality of communication through an insecure channel and protects against unauthorized alteration of data. Again, data security uses a cryptographic system to transform a plain text into a cipher text with the aid of a key. Cryptography provide the knowledge of dealing with the principles of transfer of information as secure data and when even the communication channel data is insecure (Lawnik *et al.*, 2022).

Data encryption standard (DES) algorithm accepts a series of main text with constant length as input and output is produced when the input has completed its work. A key is used for encryption and only those who know the key value can decode it. Data encryption standard is a mathematics algorithm useful for encryption and decryption of coded binary data. The data are recovered by the cipher if the same key used for decryption was used for encryption (Akshitha, 2020).

Data encryption standard contains repetitions of plaintext transformation by substitution and transposition techniques. The private key encryption only applies one key for encryption and decryption, as such the position of the key should be confidential to

the sender and receiver as the algorithm is in the public (Boateng *et al.*, 2017).

DES Key is an 8-bit sequence, the 7-bit key is among each bit and a parity bit. During cryptography, data encryption standard algorithm breaks the main text into 64-bits blocks. This algorithm works on a block which is broken into half and encryption performed on each half character by character. Characters are permuted 16 times under the key supervision and finally an encrypted 64-bit text is produced. The key with 56 bit is useful and 8-bit is for parity (Schneier *et al.*, 2016).

In this paper, triple data encryption algorithm that uses double exclusive (XOR) was used for effective data security and privacy. Cryptography provides various algorithms to secure the data. Triple Data encryption standard (Triple-DES) algorithm uses the data encryption standard block thrice to reinforce the encryption and decryption strength of data encryption standard through the triple key to improve the key size to 192 bit (Shamly and Senthilkmar, 2018).

1.2 Literature Review

Osama and Sajjad, (2025) enhanced data security using a multi-layer encryption system. The authors modified a model for the advanced encryption standards (AES) algorithm with a new key. The parameters used were encrypted using Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) and precaution were taken to ensure the security of the encryption key. The results shows that the first layer performed the advanced encryption standard for encryption time of more than 3 seconds and information decryption of less than 0.01 seconds. Also, the multi-stage encryption and decryption system demonstrates its efficiency in protecting text documents.

Opeyemi *et al.*, 2025 carryout a multimedia encryption approach by convolutional neural networks (CNN). Their works employs a CNN auto encoder architecture to extract features

from multimedia files using advanced encryption standard algorithm. The results obtained indicates that the hybrid CNN model receives an accuracy of 86% at 200 epochs with a throughput of 4,128,251 images per second and latency of 3.5 seconds at 1000 epochs.

Aru *et al.*, 2024 investigated the effect of double exclusive OR operation in triple data encryption algorithms. The technique used involves the design of triple data encryption algorithm that make use of three and two keys. Their results shows that the execution speed of triple data encryption algorithm with double exclusive OR (DXOR) was faster than triple data encryption algorithm without double

exclusive. Also, for a file size of 1MB and 15MB, the average response time was 0.15 and 2.13 seconds.

1.3 Symmetric and Public Key Algorithms

Encryption/decryption methods fall into two categories, namely symmetric key and public key. In symmetric key algorithms, the encryption and decryption keys are known both to the sender and the receiver. The encryption key is shared and the decryption key is easily calculated from it. Sometimes, the encryption and decryption keys are the same. In public key cryptography, encryption key is made public. To secure a network, the model given in Fig. 1 can be useful

Fig. 1: Model for Network Security (Shnishah, 2020)

A message to be transferred from one party to another across the internet are made through two parties and the parties must cooperate for the exchange to take place. A logical information channel is established by defining a route through the internet from source to destination and by the cooperative use of communication protocols such as transmission control protocol/internet protocol by the two parties. To achieve this, there must be a sender and a recipient who should share a common

key using conventional or private-key methods (Weiqiang *et al.*, 2021) as shown in Fig. 2.

The encryption process consists of an algorithm and a key. The key is a value independent of the plaintext. Changing the key changes the output of the algorithm. Once the cipher text is produced, it can be transmitted. Upon reception, the cipher text can be transformed back to the original plaintext by using a decryption algorithm and the same key that was used for encryption. The security

depends on several factors. Firstly, the encryption algorithm must be powerful to decrypt a message on the basis of cipher text alone. Again, the security depends on the secrecy of the key but not the secrecy of the algorithm (Sascha et al., 2019).

2.0 Materials and Methods

The materials needed for the development of a secure triple data encryption algorithm are virtual web Server for system demonstration, MATLAB/Simulink integrated development environment (IDE) application for simulation

and validation of result, Visual Studio IDE for coding, 3.4 GHz central processing unit and Windows based system equipped with 32 GB of memory.

The technique of triple data encryption was used which applies 16 round for the processing to encrypt the message in data encryption standard. The output after the 16 round consists of 64 bits that was the function of the input message and key.

Fig. 2: Diagram of Data Encryption Standard Algorithm

The triple data encryption algorithm with double exclusive OR operation implements the data thrice while the data encryption algorithm implements once with three different sets of keys. Again, the data encryption algorithm on the original text was performed using the first key K_1 to acquire the encrypted text. Also, it performs the data encryption algorithm on the encrypted text with the second key K_2 and the same process was done for the second cipher text to get the third cipher text. The exclusive

OR operation was performed twice at each of the three operations.

The encryption process started with the selection of input text from a set of data and converted to a set of binary bits to be encrypted. This encryption followed a series of compression, division, permutation and a combination of all the processes. At the end of the initial permutation, the expanded right plain text was exclusively ORed with the available key for each of the 16 rounds as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Values of Exclusive ORed Operation for 16 Round

R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R1							
									0	1	2	3	4	5	6	
0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1

3.0 Results and Discussion

The experiment was conducted on various types of files over the internet and their performance was compared with different file size, key size, file type, throughput, encryption and decryption time. The encryption time was measured at the start and end time of the data encryption process. The performance evaluation was carried out for single data encryption algorithm with double exclusive ORed operation, Triple DEA with double exclusive ORed operation with 3 keys, Triple

DEA with double exclusive ORed operation with 2 keys and each of the algorithm was processed for a period of 100 times. The results obtained reveals that the execution time increased linearly due to the increased of packet size. The performance of encryption running time, throughput and security metrics were evaluated and compared with the Avalanche effect security metric. Table 2 shows the DEA simulation parameters of the data encryption algorithm.

Table 2: Simulation Parameters of Data Encryption Algorithm

Algorithm	Key size (bits)	Block size (bits)	Number of keys
DEA	64	64	K ₁
TDEA with double exclusive ORed (3 keys)	192	64	K ₁ , K ₂ , K ₃
TDEA with double exclusive ORed (2 keys)	192	64	K ₁ , K ₂ , K ₁

Table 3: Encryption Time for Different File Size

File size (KB)	DEA	TDEA (3 KEYS)	TDEA (2 KEYS)	TDEA (3 KEYS)+DXOR	TDEA (2 KEYS)+DXOR
30	0.201	0.701	0.405	0.502	0.513
125	0.351	1.150	1.013	0.923	0.625
200	0.462	1.621	1.327	1.230	0.924
245	0.583	1.830	1.640	1.552	0.951
280	0.634	2.041	1.930	1.534	1.308
300	0.652	2.600	2.245	1.701	1.440

Fig. 3: Plot of Encryption Time against File Size

The performance evaluation based on encryption time in Table 3 confirmed that DEA

provide a better choice when less memory was used compared to when the memory was high

and the TDEA (2 KEYS) + (DXOR) became the best. Different sizes of files were used to evaluate the performance as shown in Fig. 3. The results showed that the encryption time in DEA was less than TDEA. With the implementation of DXOR, the execution time

became reduced with increase in the avalanche of the algorithm. This indicates that TDEA (2 KEYS) + DXOR was better than the TDEA (2 KEYS) and the TDEA (3 KEYS) + DXOR, respectively.

Table 4: Response Time for Data Encryption Algorithm

File size (MB)	Average Response Time				
	DEA	TDEA (3 KEYS)	TDEA (3 KEYS)+DXOR	TDEA (2 KEYS)	TDEA (3 KEYS)+DXOR
1	0.20	0.46	0.31	0.32	0.30
3	0.54	1.76	1.62	1.24	1.10
7	1.42	3.92	3.76	2.41	2.22
10	2.04	6.45	6.33	4.10	3.62

In Fig. 4, the results obtained indicates that TDEA (2KEY)+DXOR produced the best response time followed by TDEA (3KEY)+DXOR as shown in Fig. 4. The improvement in response time of TDEA was as a result of reduction encryption time. The performance analysis of DEA, TDEA(3KEYS), TDEA(2KEYS), TDEA(3KEYS)+DXOR and TDEA(2KEYS)+DXOR was done based on average response time with different data size of 1, 3, 7 and 10MB.

In Table 4, DEA has a better rising response time as file size increases and this was as a result of the security strength of the algorithm.

It was observed from Fig. that at a file of 1MB, DEA had the lowest value average response time of 0.08 seconds while TDEA (3KEYS) had the highest value of 0.42 seconds. Also, at a file size of 3MB, TDEA (3 KEYS) had the highest average response time of 1.6 while DEA had the lowest value of 0.48 seconds. At a file size of 7MB, DEA had the lowest average response time of 1.40 seconds while TDEA (3 KEYS) had the highest value of 3.90 seconds. Again, at a file size of 10MB, DEA had the lowest average response time of 2.08 seconds while TDEA (3 KEYS) had the highest value of 6.42 seconds.

Fig. 4: Plot Showing Average Response Time for DEA Algorithm

Table 5: Throughput Values for DEA Algorithms

TEXT FILE SIZE (Kb)	Execution Time (sec)				
	DEA	TDEA (3 KEYS)	TDEA (3 KEYS)+DXOR	TDEA (2 KEYS)	TDEA (3 KEYS)+DXOR
40	62	62	58	58	46
152	79	79	65	65	57
308	68	78	69	71	61
456	88	98	82	85	74
922	145	158	94	112	84
1120	198	198	111	157	201
8210	275	301	142	210	123
10,256	320	354	165	267	141
12,284	398	420	186	399	169
25,442	1670	1873	205	1223	188
57,300	2050	2670	245	1977	210
120,424	2800	3298	297	2659	261
148,446	3210	3769	333	3034	300
Avg. time	874.08	1027.54	157.84	747.46	147.30
Throughput	33.91	28.84	187.80	39.65	201.24

Fig. 5: Plot of Throughput against DEA Algorithms

Throughput describes the rate at which data is transferred based on the design encryption algorithm. Table 5 presents the throughput values of the algorithm for the selected text file sizes. The throughput values are obtained by dividing the average file size by the average execution time.

The TDEA (2KEYS) + DXOR was more efficient than the other algorithms with an estimated throughput value of 201.24 MB/s, which is 6 times greater than DEA and 9 times greater than TDEA. This indicates that the more the throughput, the more the speed and also reduction of power consumption of the algorithm. Also, it was observed that DEA had better throughput as compared to the TDEA (3KEYS) having the least performance of 28.84 Mb/sec.

The algorithms used considered the security requirements such as computational resources availability, the application's requirements, speed, execution time, encryption and

decryption time and the distribution of secure key. In order to apply appropriate encryption algorithm for the applications, knowledge about the strength, weakness, and performance based on different parameters were known.

4.0 Conclusion

Generally, most of the results obtained from these algorithms focused on evaluation parameters like encryption and decryption time, memory, avalanche effect and throughput and it shows that these parameters had better security, confidentiality, integrity and reliability for secure communication.

Again, TDEA without DXOR shows the lowest performance since it uses 64 bits block size and 168, 112 bits keys that had no modification from DEA except it improvement on the decryption time and security strength. However, its effect on throughput and encryption were poor and also, DEA and TDEA algorithms were not efficient.

In conclusion, the TDEA (2KEYS) + DXOR and TDEA (3KEYS) + DXOR should be employed in those applications where integrity, security and confidentiality are the highest priority. Again, DEA provided greater performance when speed was required during encryption and decryption at a large data rate. Based on the finding and the above conclusion, we recommend that, it is necessary to develop a hybrid encryption algorithm which will combines different encryption algorithms based on available parameters that would be used to enhance the general security of the encryption techniques.

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Declarations

Ethics and Consent to Participate

Not applicable.

Consent to Publish

Not applicable

Availability of data and materials

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